

References

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1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-4-mono arylidene-2-pyrazolin-5-thione: 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-thione₂ (0.01 mole) was dissolved in abs. ethanol (20 ml). To it aryl aldehyde (0.01 mole) and piperidine (0.5 ml) were added. The solution was allowed to stand at the room temperature overnight. The excess of the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. Since on cooling no solid was obtained the gummy mass was treated with few drops of dil. HCl and allowed to stand for some time. The solid thus obtained was filtered, washed repeatedly with distilled water and finally crystallised from ethanol. The m. p. and analytical data of the compounds are listed in Table I.

TABLE I

Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of 1-Phenyl-3-Methyl-4-Mono Arylidene-2-Pyrazolin-5-Thione

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IN our previous work on heterocyclic fungicides¹⁻⁴ it has been observed that heterocyclic five membered carbonyl compound 5-pyrazolone possess significant fungicidal activity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* which is responsible for the fatal blast disease of the rice crop. Further it has been observed that the replacement of the carbonyl oxygen atom by sulphur enhances the fungicidal activity markedly⁴. It has been earlier reported from this laboratory that 4-mono arylidene derivatives of 5-pyrazolone exhibit significant fungicidal activity^{1,5}. The present investigation was taken up with a view to study and compare the fungitoxicity of 4-mono arylidene derivatives of thio pyrazolone with those of the corresponding oxygenated compound. Treatment of 5-pyrazolone with P₂S₅ affords 5-thiopyrazolone⁴ which on condensation with the aryl aldehydes in the presence of ethanol and piperidine gave the mono-4-arylidene derivatives. The formation of this compound has been established from the satisfactory analytical values, insolubility in dil. NaOH and negative test with ethanolic FeCl₃. Ten such compounds thus prepared were screened for their antifungal activity against the rice blast pathogen *P. oryzae* by the standard method⁶ using spore germination tests at various concentrations. 5-Thiopyrazolone inhibited 81% of spore germination of *P. oryzae* at 1000 ppm concentration while its 4-mono arylidene derivatives displayed poor activity against the same pathogen. On comparison of the activity of the 4-mono arylidene derivative of 5-pyrazolone with the corresponding sulphur analogue it was observed that 4-mono arylidene derivative of 5-pyrazolone is more active than the corresponding sulphur analogue.

Sl. No.	R	m. p. (°C)	N(%) Found (Calc.)	S(%) Found (Calc.)
1.	Phenyl	195	10.00 (10.07)	11.48 (11.51)
2.	Fnyl	230 (d)	10.23 (10.44)	12.1 (11.94)
3.	<i>p</i> -anisyl	180	8.92 (9.09)	10.30 (10.38)
4.	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ Phenyl	300	13.11 (13.08)	9.78 (9.96)
5.	<i>o</i> -Cl phenyl	198-200	8.91 (8.97)	10.31 (10.25)
6.	<i>p</i> -OH phenyl	175	9.41 (9.52)	10.69 (10.88)
7.	<i>o</i> -OH phenyl	178	9.39 (9.52)	10.72 (10.88)
8.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ phenyl	163	12.94 (13.00)	9.78 (9.90)
9.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ phenyl	250	12.91 (13.00)	9.75 (9.90)
10.	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ phenyl	248	12.93 (13.00)	9.81 (9.90)

Yield of the compounds varied between 35-40%.

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by condensing 4-[N, N Bis-(2-chloroethyl) amino] benzaldehyde cyanohydrin with different amines⁴. The nitriles were treated with conc. sulphuric acid in order to get corresponding amides⁵. All the nitriles and amides were tested for antibacterial activity.

Where R=aryl, X = CN or CONH₂

Preparation and Antibacterial Activity of α -arylamino-[N, N bis-(2 chloroethyl)-amino]-Phenyl Acetonitriles and their Corresponding Amides

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THE majority of nitrogen mustard characterised by Bis-(2 chloroethyl)-amino group have been synthesised as anticancer agents¹. The property of nitrogen mustard vary widely with structural modification. Popp and Kirsch² prepared anil derivatives of 4-[N, N Bis-(2-chloroethyl)-amino]-benzaldehyde and tested against Dunning leukemia in rats. The hydrazones and thiosemicarbazones of above aldehyde have been prepared for anticancer activity^{3,4}. In view of this valid observation, we have synthesised various α -Arylamino-[N, N bis-(2 chloroethyl)-amino]-phenyl acetonitriles and their corresponding amides of type (I)

Experimental

a) Preparation of 4-[N, N Bis-(2-chloroethyl)-amino] benzaldehyde :

N, N Bis-(2 hydroxyethyl)-aniline was prepared by condensing aniline with ethylene chlorohydrine⁵. The product was then treated with dimethylformamide and phosphorus oxychloride to get the above aldehyde⁷.

b) Preparation of α -Arylamino-[N, N bis (2-chloroethyl)-amino]-phenyl acetonitriles :

The above aldehyde (0.01 mole) dissolved in ethanol (95%, 50 ml.) was added potassium cyanide (0.01 mole) in water (10 ml.) followed by glacial acetic acid (0.01 mole) with constant stirring. Amine (0.01 mole) dissolved in ethanol (95%, 85 ml.) was added and the reaction mixture kept at 25-30° for 24 hrs. The contents were diluted with cold water and the product obtained was crystallised from aqueous ethanol. (Physical. constants are recorded in table-1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF NITRILES

Sr. No.	R	Molecular formula	m. p. °C	Yield %	Calc. % Nitrogen	found
1.	Phenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₂ Cl ₂	100-01	89.2	12.06	12.0
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₂ Cl ₂	85-86	86.0	11.60	11.2
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₂ Cl ₂	120-21	81.1	11.60	11.5
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₂ Cl ₂	94-95	89.2	11.60	11.0
5.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON ₂ Cl ₂	104-05	73.2	11.11	11.3
6.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON ₂ Cl ₂	78-79	71.0	11.11	11.0
7.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON ₂ Cl ₂	75-76	89.0	11.11	10.9
8.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ Cl ₃	103-04	88.2	10.99	10.8
9.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ Cl ₃	120-21	77.0	10.99	11.1
10.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ Cl ₃	80-81	91.0	10.99	11.2
11.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ Cl ₂ Br	87-88	88.2	9.83	9.5
12.	<i>p</i> -Arsenophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ AS	79-81	87.0	10.90	10.5